

Volume 15, 27 May 2015

Publisher: Uopen Journals

URL: <http://www.ijic.org>

Cite this as: Int J Integr Care 2015; Annual Conf Suppl; [URN:NBN:NL:UI:10-1-116981](https://nbn-resolving.org/urn:nbn:nl:ui:10-1-116981)

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Conference Abstract

“Care to go”: one-stop shop solutions to foster integration. Case studies and lessons from Italy.

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Abstract

Introduction: Health and social care policy makers in Italy are facing today the hard challenge to improve integration between different typologies of care. Current features of the two sectors foster the development of different settings of care with poor coordination at the organisational and service delivery level (following Kodner, 2002, definition). This produces high costs for families and users who become case managers they themselves, and have to ride out a real “labyrinth” when accessing the care system. Many managerial and operational solutions have been implemented in Italy to help citizens and foster integration, and among them the “one-stop shop” solution, that is the subject of this research, had a broad diffusion.

Theory/Methods: Our study is based on a rich collection of case studies that are representative of the different initiatives that have been put in place in Italy following the “one-stop shop” solution for care integration. After having selected in three Italian Regions some relevant case studies in terms of size and innovative approach, we compare the organisational settings and the service delivery processes of the “one-stop shop” models to assess the impact that they can have on care integration.

Results: ven if the different initiatives put into place by the different Regions are all labelled as “one-stop shop”, they present different characteristics and have different impact on integration of care, mainly depending on the governance that has been designed and on the mission that has been appointed to them at their establishment.

Discussion: The case studies we have collected show that in Italy the “one-stop” shop solution has been developed moving from different organisational solutions and, more importantly, with different missions: sharing of data and information, reservations and booking, counselling, case management, gate keeping, needs evaluation, compliance and control,... . We have observed that

the matching between the organisational features and the fulfilled mission, determines different impact on integration of care.

Conclusion: Our research shows that the “one-stop shop” model, in Italy and elsewhere, can help integration of care and can support citizens in their care pathways but only if the implications of its organisational settings and mission are taken into account by policy makers and are coherent with one another.

Lesson learned: When designing “one-stop shop” solutions, policy makers should have clear in mind which is the mission that they want to appoint to it and follow a design process that can clearly allocate tasks and responsibilities, define the general governance and confer proper instruments.

Limitations and Suggestion for future research: The study is based on multiple case studies from three Regions in Italy: to increase its representativeness it could be extended to other Regions and countries in Europe.

Keywords

one-stop shop; case management; implementation

References

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PowerPoint presentation

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